

Amperometric Study on the Compositions of Polytungstates

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The course of reactions between thalious sulphate and different alkali tungstates (normal, di, para, tri, and meta) has been investigated by means of amperometric titrations between the reactants at different pH ranges in aqueous ethanolic media, with each of the reagents alternately as the titrant. The end points obtained from the well-defined breaks provide cogent evidence for the formation and precipitation of normal $Tl_2O \cdot WO_3$, para- $Tl_2O \cdot 2.33WO_3$ and tri- $Tl_2O \cdot 3WO_3$ tungstates of thallium (I) in the pH ranges (7.2-7.6), (5.0-5.7), (4.3-4.8) respectively. Titrations with other electrometric techniques fail to provide any dependable information regarding the compositions of thalious polytungstates.

An outstanding characteristic of the tungstates is their strong tendency to form condensed complex ions in solution, as revealed by the observations of Jander and Jahr¹; from these, polytungstates crystallise, depending on the H^+ -ion concentration which plays an important role in the aggregation process. The existence of polytungstates is usually attributed to combination with the corresponding acids as if these were separate chemical individuals. This led the previous workers to believe that similar salts of heavy metals might be precipitated as a result of metathesis². Britton and German³, however, contended that corresponding salts of heavy metals were not precipitated by the interaction of respective salts and different alkali tungstates.

There is hardly any reference in literature regarding the electrometric investigations on these reactions; the only available reference is of Flemming⁴ who reported the formation of normal thalious tungstate by mixing sodium tungstate and thalious salt and by boiling tungstic acid with thalious carbonate. His results, however, could not be confirmed later on. It has therefore been considered worthwhile to investigate precisely the compositions of thalious tungstates obtained by the interaction of thalious salt and various alkali tungstates at different pH ranges by recent electrometric techniques including amperometry, potentiometry, pH, and conductometry.

EXPERIMENTAL

AnalaR (B.D.H.) Tl_2SO_4 , Na_2WO_4 , KNO_3 , thymol, and HNO_3 were used. Air-free conductivity water was used for the preparation and subsequent dilutions of the solutions.

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1. *Z. anorg. allg. Chem.*, 1930, 194, 383.

2. F. Abegg, "Handbuch der anorganischen Chemie" Vol IV, Leipzig, 1921, pp. 577-78, 636.

3. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1429.

4. *Jena Zeit.*, 1868, 4, 34; *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1858, ii, 10, 235.

A manual polarograph with Scalamp galvanometer was used for polarographic and amperometric work. A dropping mercury electrode having the following characteristics: $m=2.416$ mg./sec., $t=3.58$ sec., and $m^{2/3} t^{1/6}=2.226$ mg.^{2/3} sec.^{-1/2} at $E_{d.e.} = -1.0$ v (vs. S.C.E.) was used in conjunction with a saturated calomel electrode connected to the cell by low-resistance salt bridge. All the amperometric titrations were carried out at an applied potential of -0.7 v in presence of KNO_3 as base electrolyte and 0.01% thymol as the maximum suppressor. The titre solution (20 ml) was taken in the cell each time, deaerated, and stirred by bubbling hydrogen. After each addition of the titrant, the galvanometer deflection was noted, corresponding current calculated, corrected for dilution effect, and plotted against the volume of titrant added in ml. The linearity of thalious-ion concentration with its wave height has been tested.

FIG. 1

Curve I(D)—ml of $M/10-Tl_2SO_4$ added to 20 ml of $M/50-Na_2WO_4$.
 Curve II(R)—ml of $M/10-Na_2WO_4$ added to 20 ml of $M/50-Tl_2SO_4$.

Amperometric Titrations.—The various alkali tungstate (di, para, tri, and meta) solutions were prepared by the action of requisite quantities of HNO_3 on standard normal sodium tungstate solution at 100° . A series of amperometric titrations was then carried out between Tl_2SO_4 and each of the different alkali tungstate solutions at various concentrations in presence of 30-60% ethanolic media, using each of the reagents alternately as titrant. When Tl_2SO_4 was used as the titrant, the titrations were performed in absence of supporting electrolyte, whereas in the reverse case, titrations were carried out in presence of appropriate concentrations of the base electrolyte KNO_3 . The results of amperometric titrations are summarised in Table I. Only three representative figures have been presented for the sake of brevity.

TABLE I

Summary of the results of amperometric titrations.

Concentrations.		Equivalence points (ml).	
Tl ₂ SO ₄ .	Na ₂ WO ₄ .	Calc.	Observed.
		Normal tungstate.	Direct titrations (Fig. 1, curve ID).
M/10	M/50	4.00	4.00
M/15	M/80	3.75	3.70
M/30	M/200	3.00	3.05
M/50	M/300	3.33	3.40
			Reverse titrations (Fig. 1, curve IIR).
M/50	M/10	4.00	3.95
M/80	M/15	3.75	3.75
M/150	M/25	3.33	3.30
M/250	M/40	3.20	3.25
	Na ₂ O.2.33WO ₃ .	Paratungstate.	Direct titrations (Fig. 2, curve ID).
M/40	M/250	3.20	3.20
M/75	M/500	3.00	3.00
M/125	M/750	3.33	3.35
M/200	M/1000	4.00	4.05
			Reverse titrations (Fig. 2, curve IIR).
M/120	M/20	3.33	3.30
M/250	M/40	3.20	3.20
M/500	M/75	3.00	3.05
M/1000	M/200	4.00	3.85
	Na ₂ O.3WO ₃ .	Tritungstate.	Direct titrations (Fig. 3, curve ID).
M/10	M/75	2.66	2.70
M/30	M/150	4.00	3.95
M/50	M/300	3.33	3.30
M/75	M/500	3.00	3.10
			Reverse titrations (Fig. 3, curve IIR).
M/100	M/15	3.00	3.00
M/150	M/25	3.33	3.30
M/250	M/40	3.20	3.15
M/400	M/70	3.50	3.40

DISCUSSION

That the formation of various polytungstates corresponds to the different stages in the anomalous neutralisation of Na tungstate by different acids, as indicated by the changes in H⁺-ion concentration, has already been shown⁵. It is considered therefore that any interaction of alkali tungstate and metal salt in solution would be largely governed by H⁺-ion concentration that would be set up by the reactants and these in turn would have pronounced influence on the composition of the precipitates. A series of reactions between thallos salt and each of the alkali tungstates has therefore been studied by electrometric techniques at different pH ranges.

5. Saxena and Sharma, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1964, **333**, 154.

As no electrode, reversible to the Tl^+ , is known and because pure thallium metal electrode, immersed in alkali tungstate solution, shows precipitations, potentiometric titrations could not be carried out. pH -titrations were also attempted, but these failed to yield any appreciable inflection in the curves because of the small difference in the pH values of Na tungstate (7.8) and the pH range (7.2-7.6) at which the quantitative precipitation of $Tl(I)$ tungstate took place. Conductometric titrations showed very feeble breaks which did not yield reproducible and dependable results. Amperometric titrations, however, yielded very precise and reproducible end points. Hence a detailed study of the course of reactions between thalious sulphate and alkali tungstate has been made by amperometric method.

$M/40-Tl_2SO_4 (ml).$

FIG 2.

FIG. 2. Curve I(D)—ml of $M/40-Tl_2SO_4$ added to 20 ml of $M/250-Na_2O \cdot 2.33 WO_3$.
Curve II(R)— „ $M/20-Na_2O \cdot 2.33 WO_3$ added to 20 ml of $M/120-Tl_2SO_4$.

$M/10-Tl_2SO_4 (ml).$

FIG 3.

FIG. 3. Curve I(D)— „ $M/10-Tl_2SO_4$ added to 20 ml $M/75-Na_2O \cdot 3 WO_3$.
Curve II(R)— „ $M/15-Na_2O \cdot 3WO_3$ added to 20 ml. of $M/100-Tl_2SO_4$.

Normal Tungstate Titrations.—Using different concentrations of Tl_2SO_4 and Na_2WO_4 solutions, amperometric titrations were carried out at $E_{d.e.} = -0.7v$, at which Tl^+ ions yielded complete diffusion current, whereas WO_4^{2-} ions did not produce any wave. In case of titrations, when thalious salt was added to Na_2WO_4 taken in cell (Fig. 1, curve ID), the diffusion current was found to remain almost constant till the stoichiometric end point was reached, beyond which it increased linearly with the increase in Tl^+ -ion concentration. In the case, when Na tungstate was used as the titrant, the reverse phenomenon was observed (Fig. 1, curve IIR). The equivalence point obtained from the point of intersection of two linear branches of the curve occurs at a stage where the molecular ratio of the reacting species $Tl_2O : WO_3$ is 1:1, corresponding to the formation of normal thalious tungstate $Tl_2O : WO_3$ in the pH range 7.2-7.6 according to the equation:

Di- and Para-tungstate Titrations.—The solution Na-ditungstate was prepared by

neutralising 0.5 moles of Na_2O per mole of Na_2WO_4 at 100° with requisite amounts of HNO_3 and its reaction with Tl_2SO_4 studied amperometrically. On examining the results, an interesting phenomenon was observed that in spite of the well-defined breaks occurring for the precipitation of thallos ditungstate, on calculation it was found to coincide with the stoichiometric end point corresponding to the formation of thallos paratungstate, $\text{Tl}_2\text{O} \cdot 2.33\text{WO}_3$. Its formation has been further confirmed by performing a series of amperometric titrations between Tl_2SO_4 and $\text{Na}_2\text{O} \cdot 2.33\text{WO}_3$ solutions with each of the reagents alternately using as the titre (Fig. 2, curves ID & IIR). The reaction taking place at pH range 5.0-5.7 can be represented as :

Tritungstate Titrations.—Fig. 3. (curves I & II) illustrates the changes occurring in diffusion current during the amperometric titrations between thallos salt and alkali tritungstate. The equivalence points obtained from the sharp break in titration curves suggest the formation of thallos tritungstate having the molecular composition $\text{Tl}_2\text{O} \cdot 3\text{WO}_3$ in the pH range 4.3-4.8 in accordance with the equations:

Similar titrations were also performed with a view to studying the reaction between Tl_2SO_4 and alkali metatungstate, but these failed to provide any dependable results.

The titrations using Tl_2SO_4 as titrant were performed in absence of any supporting electrolyte, whereas in the reverse case appropriate concentrations of the base electrolyte KNO_3 were used. The reason is that the neutral salt formed during the reaction up to the end point is sufficient to counteract the effect of migration currents. All the amperometric titrations were performed in presence of 30-60% ethanolic media on account of the appreciable solubility of the precipitates obtained.

The present investigation confirms the formation and precipitation of normal, para, and tri tungstates of thallium (I) having the compositions Tl_2WO_4 , $\text{Tl}_2\text{O} \cdot 2.33\text{WO}_3$, and $\text{Tl}_2\text{O} \cdot 3\text{WO}_3$ in the pH ranges 7.2-7.6, 5.0-5.7, and 4.3-4.8, respectively. The accuracy and reproducibility of these titrations have been found to be excellent over the range of concentrations studied. The precipitation of thallos paratungstate is almost quantitative and this reaction can be utilised for the determination of thallium (I).

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